

**MODIFIED MORI-TANAKA METHODS FOR DAMAGE MODELLING
OF SHORT FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES**Atul Jain¹

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur, West Bengal,
India 721302
atuljain@mech.iitkgp.ac.in

Keywords: Homogenization, Micro-Mechanics, Stress Localization, Finite elements

ABSTRACT

The Mori-Tanaka (MT) formulation is a commonly used method for homogenization of different types of composite materials. One of the frequent criticism of this method is the inability of the method to correctly predict the local stresses, this inability is due to the fact the MT formulation is based on the phase average calculations arising from the mean field assumptions. This paper relooks the multistep MT formulation for calculating the average stresses in individual inclusions. The average stresses in individual inclusions are compared with full FE results. It is seen that the multistep MT formulation with random increments is a feasible method for calculation of variation in the stresses in individual inclusions. However, the multistep MT formulation tends to over predict the effective modulus as compared to single step MT formulation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Homogenization and non-linear material modelling (including damage) of composites is a problem of fundamental interest for researchers in composites. There are large number of known methods by which one could homogenize composite materials. For example, a finite element (FE) model of a RVE could be built and damage be modelled on the local stress prediction [1]. Another possibility is asymptotic homogenization, Kalamkarov *et al.* [2]. A commonly used methodology is the family of methods known as mean field homogenization (MFH). A large number of variants of the MFH formulation have been developed. Different MFH formulations like the Mori-Tanaka (MT) formulation [3], self-consistent (SC) schemes [4,5] and double interpolative (DI) inclusion [6] have been used for micromechanics and homogenization of composites having wide range of fibre architecture, damage and defects. An in-depth review of use of MFH methods for composites with varied reinforcement architecture including continuous straight, discontinuous short, discontinuous curved or wavy (including nano-tubes), textile and fibers with imperfect interphases reinforcements is presented in a recent review paper [7]. MFH methods are computationally cheap, easy to set up and reasonably accurate for effective properties. They have been incorporated into number of commercial software used by various industries in the automotive and aerospace sector for design of composite components [8]. However, improvements in the computational resources now at the disposal of the researcher have decreased to some extent the low computation cost advantage of the MFH methods. Development of non-linear material modelling using MFH models is very relevant since the computational cost associated with full-field simulations (like asymptotic homogenization, variational analysis) in the nonlinear regime is still very high.

One of the major bottleneck towards development of non-linear material models within the MFH framework is the inability of these methods to derive accurately the local stresses. Jain *et al.* [9,10] validated the predictive abilities of the MT formulation to stresses in individual inclusion by comparing the MT predictions with full field FE results. It was confirmed that the MT formulation does a decent job of predicting the phase average stresses. However, they also noted that the inclusion average stress varies from inclusion to inclusion even if they have the same orientation and length. This was due to the fact that the stress in an inclusion depends on the local neighborhood. The spatial placement of inclusions is random and thus the immediate neighborhood of inclusions can be different. The MFH formulation failed to capture this effect. The estimation of average stresses in individual inclusions is critical for developing models for fibre related damage and non-linear effects.

There have been limited attempts at incorporating stochastic effects within the framework of the MT formulation. Rafiee [11] used the MT formulation for homogenization of wavy fibre composites. It was proposed to replace the wavy fibre by the horizontal and vertical projections of the fibre. The effective properties of the composite were then individually calculated for both cases as possible bounds of possible stiffness using MFH methods. Subsequently, a random number between the two bounds is ascribed to the unit cell to account for the variation in the shape of the wavy inclusion.

This paper proposes a modified approach to MT formulation so that the stress variation in individual inclusions within one phase can be accounted for. The proposed method is a variant of the multi-step MT formulation which was first proposed by Zouri et al. [12] and recently elaborated by Abaimov et al. [13]. The aim is to develop a MFH formulation which can predict the scatter in average stresses in inclusions having same orientation and aspect ratio. Full FE results is used for validation of the proposed model.

2 THE MORI-TANAKA FORMULATION AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

A brief description of the MT formulation is provided below:

Effective stiffness of a composite is usually calculated by relating the strain concentration factor of the inclusions to the effective stiffness of the composite by the relation (Eqn. 1):

$$C^{eff} = C^m + \sum_{\alpha=1}^M c_{\alpha} (C^{\alpha} - C^m) A^{\alpha} \quad (1)$$

where, C^{eff} is the effective stiffness of the composite, C^m , C^{α} are the stiffness matrix of the matrix and inclusion respectively, c_{α} is the volume fraction of the individual inclusion, M is the total number of inclusions and A^{α} is the strain concentration factor which relates the strain in the inclusion to the applied strain.

The strain concentration tensor, A^{α} is calculated as follows:

$$A^{\alpha} = A_m^{\alpha} [c_m I + \sum_{\beta=1}^M c_{\beta} A_m^{\beta}]^{-1} \quad (2)$$

Where, A_m^{α} is the dilute strain concentration tensor relating the strain in the inclusion to the average strain in the matrix and is derived from the expression below using S^{α} the Eshelby tensor [14]. This expression of the dilute strain concentration is derived using the Mori-Tanaka' assumptions.

$$A_m^{\alpha} = [I + S^{\alpha} (C^m)^{-1} (C^{\alpha} - C^m)]^{-1} \quad (3)$$

The strain concentration tensor A^{α} which relates the strain in the inclusion to the applied strain. When this strain concentration tensor is multiplied with the applied strain, one can derive the average stress in an inclusion. Mathematically;

$$\langle \epsilon^{\alpha} \rangle = A^{\alpha} \langle \epsilon^{\infty} \rangle \quad (4)$$

ϵ^{α} and ϵ^{∞} are the average strain in phase α and the far field strain respectively and $\langle \rangle$ indicates average.

Benveniste [15] interpreted the MT formulation by considering that each inclusion behaves as an isolated inclusion subjected to a far field strain. The influence of the other inclusions is accounted for by the presence of an "image strain". The mean field assumption stipulates that the image strain is same for all the inclusions; implying each inclusions is influenced by other inclusions similarly. It is because of this simplification that the stresses in individual inclusions having same orientation and aspect ratio is calculated as the same. However, in reality the stresses in individual inclusions usually will be different. The stresses in inclusions are dependent on the immediate neighborhood of the inclusions

which vary from inclusions to inclusion due to random spatial location of the inclusions. The conventional MT formulation cannot account for this stochasticity.

It is important to clarify here some of the different terms frequently. In a composite, all inclusions having same orientation, aspect ratio and material property are termed as a phase. A composite which has all the inclusions having same material property, same aspect ratio and orientation is termed as bi-phase composite (with the matrix being the other phase), multiphase composite refers to composite where the inclusions have different aspect ratio, orientation or material property. A bi-phase composite can have several inclusions. The phase average stress implies the average stresses of inclusions over the entire phase. The inclusion average stress implies the stress average for a particular inclusion.

Micro-structure of composites having 30 inclusions with aspect ratio 3, all orientated in the same direction and the volume fraction of the inclusions was 0.161 (see **Figure 1**) was created using the random sequential adsorption algorithm [16] by Jain et al. [9]. The Elastic modulus was taken to be 72 GPa and 3 GPa respectively for the fiber and the matrix, while the Poisson's ratio was 0.37 and 0.22 respectively. The RVE was subjected to periodic boundary with loading in the fibre axis direction. The same configuration is studied in this paper.

Figure 1 Micro-structure of composite with fully aligned inclusions having aspect ratio of 3 and volume fraction of 0.161, with schematic representation of the periodic boundary condition

The predicted phase average stress was found to be 143.3 and 143.2 by the MT and FE calculations respectively. It can be seen that the match in phase average properties is very good. However, it was also reported that the FE calculations revealed large variation in the inclusion average stress with a standard deviation of 10.52 MPa. The stress contour derived from the FE result is shown in **Figure 2**; it is seen that different inclusions have different stress levels. In general, the inclusions which have more inclusions in its immediate neighborhood are more stressed.

Figure 2 The stress contour in FE volume element subjected to loading in the axial direction.

Figure 3 shows a different interpretation of the scatter in stresses in individual inclusions, in the figure the black line shows the predicted phase average stress as a function of the inclusion volume fraction as predicted by the MT formulation. The red markers show the calculated inclusion average stress in by the FE model. The inclusion volume fraction of the RVE is 0.161 and is depicted by the red dotted line. It is seen that the inclusion average stress varies from around 120 MPa to 164 MPa. According to the MT formulation, the inclusion average stress would be 120 MPa if the volume fraction of inclusions is 0.02, while the stress of 164 MPa corresponds to volume fraction of about 0.26. This variation in stress is due to the fact that due to random spatial inclusion placement the effective local volume fraction for the inclusion varies from 0.02 to about 0.26. If one were to model fibre stress dependent damage mode in composites, the inclusion with the highest stress can be expected to damage initiation point. This would be missed by the MT model and thus the damage modelling will be inaccurate. This inability of the MT formulation to predict the variation in the average stress due to difference in immediate neighborhood is a major criticism of the MT method and is seen as bottleneck for modelling damage and non-linearity in composites.

Figure 3 The scatter in individual stresses within an RVE. The RVE volume fraction is 0.161 but the average stress in individual inclusions corresponds to large range of volume fraction.

3 PROPOSED MODEL

A multistep approach to the MT formulation is suggested. This model initially proposed by Zouari *et al.* [12] was originally aimed at increasing the accuracy of the MT scheme at high inclusion volume fraction. In this paper, the scheme is adapted to account for the variation in the average stress in individual inclusion.

In this scheme, the inclusion phase is added incrementally. One starts with isotropic matrix and adds a small volume of the inclusion and the MT formulation is implemented. The homogenized material is taken to be the matrix in the next stage and a fraction of the inclusion is added to it followed by subsequent homogenization. This is repeated till all of the inclusions are accounted for. The inclusion average stresses are calculated at the end of every increment. A schematic representation of the scheme is given in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4 Schematic representation of the multistep MT formulation

Let us consider the homogenization of biphas composite with 0.25 volume fraction of the inclusion phase and 0.75 fraction of the matrix using 5 step homogenization process with equal increments. In the first step, 0.05 fraction of the inclusion will be considered and homogenized with the matrix. Thus the volume fraction of the inclusion in this step is not 0.25 but $0.05 / (0.75 + 0.05) = 0.0625$. In the next time step, 0.05 fraction of the inclusion is added to fictitious matrix (having weight 0.8, but already containing 0.05 inclusion phase) so effectively the inclusion volume fraction is higher in the next increment and so on. Thus, this method allows in an indirect manner to allot different fibre volume fraction to inclusions.

An important consideration is the calculation of the Eshelby tensor to be input in the equation 3. For ellipsoids in isotropic matrix, the Eshelby tensor is a function of the Poisson's ratio of the matrix and the geometry of the inclusion. Since the initial matrix is usually isotropic, the calculation of the Eshelby tensor is straight forward in the first increment. From the next step onwards, there are two choices: the first is to retain the Eshelby tensor calculated in the first step for all subsequent steps. The second option is to calculate the Eshelby tensor based on the properties of the homogenized material at the end of every iteration. In this paper we propose to use the first option as the Eshelby tensor signifies the Eigen strain introduced by a single inclusion in an infinite sea of matrix. This Eigen strain should not vary depending on the choice of the homogenization scheme or simplifications made during the homogenization. The properties of the homogenized matrix will be introduced in Equations 1 and 2 (presented in section 2) leading to the calculation of different image strains, strain concentration tensors and subsequently variable inclusion average stresses for different inclusions.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this paper, FE volume element with inclusions having Aspect Ratio 3 and volume fraction of 0.161 is considered. The volume element contains 30 inclusions, this number is recommended by other previous studies [17]. All the inclusions aligned in the same direction. The volume elements were subjected to periodic boundary conditions with loading in the axial and transverse direction respectively

and stress in individual inclusions are calculated. Finite element software ABAQUS[18] has been used for the calculations.

First a sensitivity study [19] of the proposed scheme is studied. A RVE with inclusions aspect ratio of 3 and volume fraction of 0.161 was considered and the multi-step MT formulation was implemented with equal increments. The number of increments is increased and the effective properties was calculated. It is seen that as the number of increments is increased the predicted effective modulus increases (**Figure 5**). However, the predicted modulus converges quickly, the converged modulus is about 5.9% higher than the modulus calculated using the single step MT formulation. This result is consistent with the results of Abaimov *et al.* [13] who reported about 5% rise in predicted modulus when differential multi-step MT formulation was used.

Figure 5 Sensitivity study of the multistep MT formulation- the effective modulus as a function of number of increments

The focus in the remaining part of the paper is about stresses in individual inclusions. A multistep MT formulation is implemented but the weightage of inclusion in every increment was random. The randomness is chosen to account for the random spatial location and immediate neighborhood of the inclusions.

First, the loading in axial direction with periodic boundary condition is considered. The predicted stresses in individual inclusions is presented in **Figure 5**. It is seen that the FE models predicted varying stresses in individual inclusions varying from 120 MPa to 164 MPa. While there is good match for the average stress in the inclusion phase by the FE models and single step MT formulation. The single step MT formulation failed to predict the varying stress level in individual inclusions. A multistep MT formulation predicts a varying level of stresses in inclusions with variation from 126 MPa to 185 MPa (**Figure 6**). The stresses in the inclusion was lowest in the first step of the multistep MT formulation and increases as the step increases. This is expected since the inclusion volume fraction is lowest in the first increment.

Figure 6 Axial stresses in individual inclusions for RVE subjected to loading in the axial direction- the black markers indicate stresses by FE calculations. The red dotted lines indicate the stress prediction by the single step MT and the multistep MT formulation

Ten realization of the multistep MT formulation with random increments was performed and the average stress in the inclusion phase is compared. It is seen that there is little variation of the average stresses in the inclusion phase, but there is slight over prediction (Figure 7). The variation in the predicted effective modulus is less than 2% within different random realizations.

Figure 7 Average axial stress in the inclusion phase for RVE subjected to axial loading. 10 realizations of random multistep MT are compared with FE results.

The same FE volume element is now subjected to load in the transverse direction. The inclusion average phase transverse stress predicted by the MT formulation and FE formulation is 56.60 and 56.71 MPa (**Figure 8**). Similar to the axial load case, there is very good match between the two schemes but expectedly, the single step MT formulation is unable to capture the stress variation in individual inclusions. The multistep MT formulation with random increments leads to better capture of the stress variation of the stresses in individual inclusions.

Figure 8 Transverse stresses in individual inclusions for RVE subjected to loading in the transverse direction—the black markers indicate stresses by FE calculations. The red dotted lines indicate the stress prediction by the single step MT and the multistep MT formulation

It is thus confirmed that the multistep MT formulation can predict the variation in average stresses without compromising significantly the accuracy of the effective properties. It can thus be a viable method for developing models which rely on inclusion stresses, for example fibre matrix debonding.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE OUTLOOK

A multistep MT formulation is described in this paper and the feasibility of this method to account for stresses in individual inclusions is studied. The multi-step MT formulation can account for stresses in individual inclusions for both loading in the axial as well as transverse loading. The predicted stresses variation is compared with FE calculations and good match is observed. It is also observed that the multistep MT formulation over predicts the effective modulus by 3-5%. This is a major development within the framework of MFH formulation and provides immense possibilities for modelling damage and non-linearity in fibre reinforced composites.

This paper exclusively deals with biphasic composites; future work will involve multiphase composites. The other possible developments include non-linearity in the matrix as well as damage modes like fibre matrix debonding and fibre damage.

6 REFERENCES

- [1] Lomov S V, Ivanov DS, Verpoest I, Zako M, Kurashiki T, Nakai H, et al. Meso-FE modelling of textile composites: Road map, data flow and algorithms. *Compos Sci Technol* 2007;67:1870–91. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2006.10.017.
- [2] Kalamkarov AL, Andrianov I V, Danishevs'kyi V V. Asymptotic Homogenization of Composite Materials and Structures. *Appl Mech Rev* 2009;62:30802–20. doi:10.1115/1.3090830.
- [3] Mori T, Tanaka K. Average Stress in Matrix and Average Elastic Energy of Materials with Misfitting Inclusions. *Acta Metall* 1973;21:571–4. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/0001-6160(73)90064-3.
- [4] Kroner E. Elastic moduli of perfectly disordered composite materials. *J Mech Phys Solids* 1967;15:319–. doi:10.1016/0022-5096(67)90026-9.
- [5] Kerner EH. The elastic and thermo-elastic properties of composite media. . *Proc Phys Soc London Sect B* 1956;69:808–13. doi:10.1088/0370-1301/69/8/305.
- [6] Lielens G. Micro-Macro Modeling of Structured Materials. Université Catholique de Louvain, Belgium, 1999.

- [7] Jain A. Micro and mesomechanics of fibre reinforced composites using mean field homogenization formulations: A review. *Mater Today Commun* 2019;Accepted. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2019.100552>.
- [8] Jain A, Verpoest I, Hack M, Lomov S, Adam L, Van Paepegem W. Fatigue Life Simulation on Fiber Reinforced Composites - Overview and Methods of Analysis for the Automotive Industry. *SAE Int J Mater Manuf* 2012;5:205–14. doi:10.4271/2012-01-0730.
- [9] Jain A, Lomov S V., Abdin Y, Verpoest I, Van Paepegem W. Pseudo-grain discretization and full Mori Tanaka formulation for random heterogeneous media: Predictive abilities for stresses in individual inclusions and the matrix. *Compos Sci Technol* 2013;87:86–93. doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2013.08.009.
- [10] Jain A, Abdin Y, Van Paepegem W, Verpoest I, Lomov S V. Effective anisotropic stiffness of inclusions with debonded interface for Eshelby-based models. *Compos Struct* 2015;131:692–706. doi:10.1016/j.compstruct.2015.06.007.
- [11] Rafiee R. Influence of carbon nanotube waviness on the stiffness reduction of CNT/polymer composites. *Compos Struct* 2013;97:304–9. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2012.10.028>.
- [12] Zouari R, Benhamida A, Dumontet H. A micromechanical iterative approach for the behavior of polydispersed composites. *Int J Solids Struct* 2008;45:3139–52. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2008.01.016>.
- [13] Abaimov SG, Trofimov A, Sergeichev I V, Akhatov IS. Multi-step homogenization in the Mori-Tanaka-Benveniste theory. *Compos Struct* 2019. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2019.03.073>.
- [14] Eshelby JD. The Determination of the Elastic Field of an Ellipsoidal Inclusion, and Related Problems. *Proc R Soc London Ser a-Mathematical Phys Sci* 1957;241:376–96. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1098/rspa.1957.0133>.
- [15] Benveniste Y. A new approach to the application of mori-tanaka theory in composite-materials. *Mech Mater* 1987;6:147–57. doi:10.1016/0167-6636(87)90005-6.
- [16] Rintoul MD, Torquato S. Reconstruction of the structure of dispersions. *J Colloid Interface Sci* 1997;186:467–76. doi:10.1006/jcis.1996.4675.
- [17] Pierard O, Friebel C, Doghri I. Mean-field homogenization of multi-phase thermo-elastic composites: a general framework and its validation. *Compos Sci Technol* 2004;64:1587–603. doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2003.11.009.
- [18] ABAQUS. A Gen Finite Elem Software, ABAQUS Inc, Pawtucket RI, USA 2019.
- [19] Jain A, Veas JMJM, Straesser S, Van Paepegem W, Verpoest I, Lomov SVS V. The Master SN curve approach - A hybrid multi-scale fatigue simulation of short fiber reinforced composites. *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf* 2016;91:510–8. doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2015.11.038.